

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D5.3

CONTROL SYSTEM FOR THE POWER ELECTRONICS AND ROTATORY TRANSFORMER ARRANGEMENT

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About XROTOR

XROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The XROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The XROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, XROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This report focuses on the improvement and control of the XROTOR power take off system, including the PMSG, the generator-side power electronics, the rotary transformer system, and its grid-side converter.

The report begins with improvements in the design of a rotary transformer configuration (i.e. a wireless power transfer system) capable to handle the MW power transfer requirement of the XROTOR system. The deliverable includes a detailed specification of the rotatory transformer including parameters such as operating frequencies, current density, windings area, air-gap length, and others. The efficiency is quantified using finite element simulation and numerical calculations. Furthermore, its thermal performance at rated power levels is analysed and quantified using finite element simulation. The simulation results show that high level of efficiency (around 98.5%) can be obtained with a proper design methodology and suitable compensation network for the transformer system.

The second section of the report provides the design and analysis of a suitable power electronic topology for the rotary transformer to manipulate the wireless power flow at the levels of efficiency required by the XROTOR project. The analysis includes electrical operation and energy conversion losses simulation of a three-phase dual active bridge configuration suitable for high-power wireless power applications. The simulation demonstrates the suitability of the topology to drive MW level power through a rotary transformer system at efficiencies of around 98%. This efficiency is calculated via electrical and thermal analysis and simulations.

Finally, a configuration of the controllers and power electronic architectures for the machine side converter and grid side converter system of the XROTOR is presented and analysed in detail.

The methodologies presented in this deliverable can be utilized to design multi-MW level rotary transformer system and associated power electronic drivers. The designed parameters utilize the standard DC voltage levels of commercial back-to-Back converter for wind generators. As such, the designs presented in this report can be incorporated as another energy conversion stage in the DC bus of a commercial Back-to-Back power electronic system.

List of acronyms

$\Delta\Delta$	Delta to delta
3P	Three phases
AC	Alternating Current
AWG	American Wire Gauge
BJT	Bipolar junction transistor
DAB	Dual-Active-Bridge
DC	Direct current
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
GSC	Generator-side Converter
IGBT	Insulated-gate bipolar transistor
IMC	Internal Model Controller
MEC	Magnetic equivalent circuit
MMF	Magneto motive Force
MOSFET	Metal–oxide–semiconductor field-effect transistor
MSC	Machine-Side Converter
MW	Mega watt
PTE	Power transfer efficiency
RMS	Root mean square
RT	Rotary transformers
VA	Voltampere
VAWT	Vertical-axis wind turbine
YY	Wye to wye
ZVS	Zero-Voltage Switching

1 Introduction

The XROTOR is a novel hybrid wind turbine concept that retains some of the advantages of a vertical-axis wind turbine (VAWT) [1, 2]. As depicted in Figure 1, the XROTOR concept has a primary vertical axis rotor consisting of an upper and lower part with relatively conventional blades that are angled both upwards and downwards from the ends of a relatively short, stiff cross-arm. The role of the upper part is to provide the major contribution to mechanical power extraction from the wind. Secondary horizontal axis rotors are attached to the lower blades of the primary rotor, which extract wind energy. This design reduces the overturning moment on the main bearing and reduces the size and weight of the rotor, thus saving on the cost of maintenance and installation. Furthermore, it can capture more energy from the wind, which greatly improves the efficiency of the machine.

In the conventional vertical axis wind turbine, the vertical axis rotor plays a role in power take-off. However, in the XROTOR, the aerodynamic torque on the primary rotor is not balanced by the reaction torque from a generator. Instead, it is balanced by the thrust on the secondary rotors. As such, the energy conversion is carried out entirely by the generators of the secondary rotors. Given the high speed of rotation of the secondary rotors, their size can be reduced. This approach can simplify the power-take-off system and reduce the weight of the wind turbine. Since the energy conversion is carried out entirely in the secondary rotor, the challenge of transmitting energy from a rotating structure to the turbine’s tower needs to be addressed.

Figure 1. Powertrain structure

2 Power Transmission System for Wind Turbine

The transmission of electrical power and signals from the stationary structure to the rotating tower is most efficiently accomplished with slip rings. There are five very important characteristics of wind turbines that require specialized slip ring design considerations [3].

Life	Continuous rotation at 30 RPM for 100 million cycles or more requires contact materials with an exceptionally good wear rate.
Environment	Contacts must be robust to survive nacelle environments. The materials must tolerate the humidity, temperature, and contamination environments that can be present, and the assembly must be appropriately sealed.
Electrical Requirements	Typical slip rings have power requirements as well as signal transfer requirements. The contact material must have good power (current) capacity as well as low contact resistance for good signal transmission.

Maintainability	Contacts should not degrade significantly with time or be subject to sudden catastrophic failure if specified inspection or maintenance procedures are followed.
Reliability	Contacts should require little or no maintenance. Any wear debris must be carefully managed to avoid arcing or short circuits.

Typically, life tests are conducted using “noise” (variation in contact resistance with rotation) as the end-of-life criteria. At the end of life, the build-up of wear debris causes a sharp increase in noise to the point where intermittent open circuits are detected. Noise values of less than 250 milliohms are well within acceptable levels for power channels. The noise values of less than 100 milliohms on the signal channels is quite acceptable for most discrete and control circuit.

2.1 Slip Rings

Brush wear is caused by electrical, mechanical, environmental/chemical, and thermal factors. Mechanically, brushes wear from friction as two surfaces slide against each other. With the operation of brushes on the collector ring, a film forms that consists of metal oxide, carbon graphite, some contamination and a small, but critical, amount of moisture. The film consists of metal oxide from the collector ring, carbon or graphite from the brushes, contaminants and a small but critical amount of water vapor from the air. The film provides a low friction surface. Electrically, material is removed from the brush by the flow of current. With increasing brush temperatures at the brush faces, some carbon also oxidizes into carbon dioxide gas. Brush wear rates increase considerably if the brush temperatures are over 150 degrees Celsius for many grades [4].

The wear of the brushes is appreciably high. The total lifetime of the rotor slip ring system with graphite/copper couples is between 6 to 12 months [5]. Therefore, very short service intervals are the consequence. The service has been carried out every 3 months by the graphite/copper couples, and the graphite brushes must be changed by the service every 6 months. The wind power industry demands service intervals for the slip ring system at least every 12 months. The development of graphite/graphite friction couples has increased the total lifetime of the brushes. The lifetime of the graphite/graphite couples is 5 years and so appreciably higher than graphite/copper couples.

The most common characteristics and issues of slip ring machines include the following [6]:

- **Sparking:** Sparking is a spontaneous occurrence resulting in damage to the surface of the slip rings. This leads to shorter intervals before the next spontaneous sparking incident. The intensity and frequency of sparking increases with an increase in rotational speed. Sparking is unaffected by the rotor electrical frequency but is affected by the eccentricity of the slip ring surface [6].
- **Contact Force:** Contact force represents the amount of force applied to the brushes to make contact with the rotor slip ring. The voltage drops across the brush contact is dependent on the contact force and increases as the contact force decreases [6].
- **Contact Area:** The contact area refers to the surface area between the brush and slip ring. The contact area directly influences the friction coefficient and mechanical losses [7].
- **S-Factor:** The S-factor refers to the amount of heat that can be dissipated at the slip ring surface and is measured in surface area per current.
- **Peripheral Coverage Ratio:** The peripheral coverage ratio refers to the ratio of slip ring periphery covered by the brushes along the tangential direction and the total slip ring periphery.

2.2 Maintenance of Slip Rings

Slip ring failure can be caused by decreasing contact force, breaking of the connecting lead or by high wear over time, resulting in a high maintenance component with short service intervals. Below tables show the maintenance intervals and wear of the brush.

Type of maintenance	Maintenance intervals of copper-graphite in years	Maintenance interval of graphite-graphite in years
Service	0.25	1
Replacement	0.5	5

Table 1: maintenance interval of different slip ring technologies [6]

Friction Couples	Wear of brush per 1000 hours
Copper-graphite	4 – 7 mm
Graphite-graphite	< 0.5 mm

Table 2: brush wear different slip ring technologies [6]

The mechanical wear is caused by the friction due to the relative movement (rotation of the slip ring) of the components on each other and the electrical wear is affected by the increasing of the contact temperature that is caused by the electrical and the friction heat. This electrical heat is influenced by the electrical resistance that plays an important role in the electrical contact. The contact pair used in this work is graphite [7].

The electrical wear is reduced with increase of the contact force, though this leads to an increased mechanical wear (Error! Reference source not found.). The higher the current amplitude, the greater the decrease in the mechanical wear in favour of the electrical wear.

Figure 2. Wear emergence on the contact wire depending on the: applied force (left), current amplitude (right) comp. [3]

There are several different brush and slip ring materials in use. Brushes are made of different carbon grades, e.g., electrographite, carbon graphite, or metal graphite, whereas slip ring materials can be copper, bronze, brass, steel [8].

Contact voltage drop-brush current (V-I) characteristic tests were conducted using a steel slip ring and silver (Ag)-graphite brushes to determine the electrical characteristics of this system. In recent years, silver (Ag)-graphite brushes and noble metal-plated slip rings are commonly used because they are regarded as being effective in reducing the contact voltage drop [9].

Figure 3. Contact voltage drop–brush current (V-I) characteristics of Ag and Au slip rings. (Ag-graphite brushes (Ag contents of 50, 70, and 90 wt.%) and noble metal-plated slip rings (silver and gold (Ag and Au)- plated).)

Figure 4. V-I characteristics of the steel slip ring (S45C) and various Ag-graphite brushes (Ag contents of 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90 wt.%)

2.3 Industrial Slip Ring System

For comparison purposes, a cost assessment would be required to compare wireless power transfer systems with slip rings.

Based on my literature review, I was unable to locate reliable data regarding slip ring maintenance and cost. Therefore, some inquiries were made to the manufacturers of industrial slip rings regarding the cost and maintenance of slip rings compatible with XROTOR (2.5 MW, 3300 V, 20 RPM).

The solution has been sent only by one manufacturer ([MOOG](#)):

"The application fits well for one of our trenching series slip rings. These units are horizontal and turn up to 60rpm. They have gold contacts that cut the resistance between the brushes and reduce the heat of the contact point. We have space to put some other cables through the bore of the unit. These units are used in a harsh environment and so are fully stainless steel and made to a very high standard. They pass all marine certification standards, electrical and mechanical. A single unit can cost CAD\$ 150,000 (about GBP 87,000). The preference for us would be to have a service performed at 5 years that would entail removal of the unit and replacement of the brushes."

Even though the active material usage for the wireless power transfer system is calculated, the waste of material and manufacturing costs are not calculated accurately.

Using two contacting bodies, power (current) can be transferred from a rotating element to a stationary one. Theoretically, this system would be efficient according to the V-I characteristics as the electrical loss of the system is not very significant. The problem arises when practical considerations are taken into account,

especially the mechanical and chemical performance of the system. A key challenge of wind turbines is maintaining the slip ring in its acceptable physical condition under the environmental and operational conditions. Consequently, maintenance becomes essential and directly affects the system's reliability. In addition to increasing O&M costs, it also requires the monitoring and fault detection systems.

3 RT for 2.5 MW Wireless Power Transfer System

Rotary transformers (RT) are adopted to transfer energy from primary to secondary in situations in which the two sides are in relative rotation. These devices are cylindrical transformers with two cores and the corresponding winding separated by an air gap.

The structure of an Induction-Based Rotary Transformer is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Rotary Transformer (RT) structure – one unit

In the previous report, detailed explanations of the principles and the design approach and analysis results were presented. This section aims to present the modified design of RT.

Based on the analytical design equations [10] and the input parameters, 2 variants of the RT were designed as shown in Table 3 and the material usage is reported in Table 4.

Design variant	1	2
g (mm)	10	10
b (mm)	40	40
l_n	300	300
w	20	15
N	14	14
<i>mutual, leakage ind.</i> (mH)	3.34 & 0.07	3.13 & 0.07
R_1, R_2 (ohm)	0.0134, 0.0144	0.0133, 0.0143
Max. power transfer (kW), (FEA, MATLAB)	(844 , 818)	(844 , 818)
core & copper loss (kW)	2.46 , 7.37	3, 7.3
Total weight (ton)	0.86	0.7
Max. winding temp. rise (°C)	118	132
Efficiency	0.989	0.988

Table 3: RT parameters

Design variant	1	2
copper weight (kg)	284	282
magnetic core material – electrical steel (kg)	571	415

Table 4: Material usage, 1 unit of 6 per tower

Supporting structures are not considered in material usage calculations, such as bearings and holders that hold the RT to the tower.

Figure 6. 3D view of 6 RTs configuration

Above figure shows the placement configuration of RTs on the shaft. Notable points are:

- Gray: primary and secondary cores,
- Orange: primary and secondary coils,
- 6 RTs are required for each tower of XROTOR,
- There should be at least a few centimetres axial space between RTs to ensure magnetic decoupling.

To ensure that no magnetic saturation occurs in the core, the RT has been simulated at its rated power operation as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Magnetic flux density distribution, 1 MVA, variant 2

In the next subsections, some concerns about the mechanical performance of RT are analysed.

3.1 Effect of Eccentricity

To analyse the eccentricity, it is assumed that the primary (inner) is moved (in x or y direction) by 2mm (20% of the airgap length) and so, the airgap is 8mm in one side and 12mm in the other side. Figure 8 shows the induced voltage, output instantaneous power, and the core loss. Based on these simulations this effect is negligible.

Figure 8. Effect of eccentricity on electrical parameters

3.2 Axial Force Analysis

The force components are shown in Figure 9 with and without the eccentricity. Eccentricity results in the force magnitude to be increased. Nevertheless, considering the simulation results the forces are small.

Figure 9. Axial force analysis

3.3 Thermal Analysis

For this analysis, convection heat transfer with the equivalent heat transfer coefficient of 30 W/m.²K is assumed. Simulation results show that the maximum temperature is in the acceptable range while it is recommended to consider some cooling system like air circulation.

Figure 10. Thermal analysis

4 Design Optimization of the PMSG

Several topologies of permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs) have also been proposed to address the issue of large-sized Direct Drive PMSGs, including outer-rotor surface mounted PMSGs, inner-rotor surface mounted PMSGs, and interior PMSGs [11]. In some research, outer-rotor is used because of their low manufacturing costs and ease of construction. To achieve high efficiency and high-power density, it is necessary to consider the cooling systems for outer-rotor structures. However, further efforts need to be made to develop machines that can reduce the weight of DD-PMSGs with high power. Researchers have previously reported difficulties scaling up to several megawatts or more. Especially for offshore applications, the resulting designs are excessively large and/or massive, which pose major logistical challenges.

For the design procedure of electric machines, several optimization algorithms have been developed to find an optimal design. The first algorithms implemented were deterministic and direct search algorithms. In the last few years, gradient-free stochastic algorithms, like particle swarm optimization and genetic algorithms (GAs), have taken over. A review of the GA shows that it is an efficient method for finding an

optimal solution for designing electric machines, allowing individuals from generations to be discarded that cannot fit constraints.

4.1 Analytical Design

PMSGs are fabricated as inner and outer rotor forms. Figure 11 shows the structures of inner-rotor and outer-rotor PMSGs. The average radius (r_g) between the stator and the rotor is considered as the air-gap radius and will be used in the analytical design equations [12].

Figure 11. The structures of inner-rotor and outer-rotor PMSGs, a) inner-rotor, b) outer-rotor, c) linearized model

In this section, based on the magnetic equivalent circuit and the flux path, the geometrical and electrical parameters are calculated.

The fundamental harmonic of the air-gap flux density due to the magnets is [13]:

$$\hat{B}_{g1} = \hat{B}_g \frac{4}{\pi} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\alpha\right); \hat{B}_g = \frac{l_m}{\mu_{rm} \cdot g_e} B_{rm} \quad 1$$

where B_{rm} is the remnant flux density of the magnets, l_m is the magnet height, α is the PM width to pole pitch ratio, and:

$$g_e = K_c \cdot g_1; g_1 = g + \frac{l_m}{\mu_{rm}} \quad 2$$

where g is the airgap length and the Carter factor is defined as:

$$K_c = \frac{\tau_{slot}}{\tau_{slot} - g_1 \cdot \gamma}; \gamma = \frac{4}{\pi} \left[\frac{w_s}{2g_1} \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{w_s}{2g_1}\right) - \log\left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{w_s}{2g_1}\right)^2}\right) \right] \quad 3$$

where w_s is the slot opening and τ_{slot} the slot pitch.

The no-load phase voltage induced by this flux density in a stator winding can be calculated as [14]:

$$E_{rms} = \sqrt{2} \cdot K_w \cdot N_{ph} \cdot \omega_m \cdot r_g \cdot L \cdot \hat{B}_{g1} \quad 4$$

where K_w is the winding factor, N_{ph} the phase number of turns, ω_m the angular mechanical speed, r_g the mean airgap radius, and L the axial length.

The winding factor for concentrated winding could be calculated by [15]:

$$K_w = \frac{\sin(\pi/6)}{q_1 \cdot \sin(\pi/(6q_1))} \quad 5$$

The stator electrical loading is defined as:

$$A = \frac{2 \cdot m \cdot N_{ph}}{2\pi \cdot r_g} I_{rms} \quad 6$$

where m is the number of phases, and I_{rms} the phase current.

So, the average apparent power transferred through the airgap over one period of the power source can be written in terms of the instantaneous induced voltage and the current equations as:

$$S_g = m \cdot E_{rms} \cdot I_{rms} = \sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \cdot r_g^2 \cdot K_w \cdot \omega_m \cdot L \cdot A \cdot \hat{B}_{g1} \quad 7$$

Moreover, the pole magnetic flux density is calculated as:

$$H_c l_m = \phi \frac{g_e}{\mu_0 w_m L} \rightarrow \phi = \frac{\mu_0 H_c l_m w_m L}{g_e} \quad 8$$

where w_m is the PM width. For the slot and tooth sizing, the maximum allowed flux density (B_t) to prevent saturation should be considered. So, the tooth width, yoke thickness, and slot width are calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} w_t &= \frac{\phi}{B_t q_1 m L} \\ L_y &= \frac{q_1 m w_t}{2} \\ w_s &= \tau_{slot} - w_t; \tau_{slot} = \frac{\pi r_g}{q_1 m \cdot p} \end{aligned} \quad 9$$

And the slot depth is calculated based on the phase current, current density (J), and slot fill factor (s_f):

$$h_s = \frac{A_s}{w_s}; A_s = \frac{I_{rms} N_{ph}}{p \cdot q_1 \cdot J \cdot s_f} \quad 10$$

where p is the number of pole pairs.

Magnetizing and leakage inductances are calculated as [16]:

$$\begin{aligned} L_m &= \mu_0 \frac{2m r_g}{\pi p^2 g_e} L (K_w N_{ph})^2 \\ L_l &= \mu_0 \frac{2}{p q_1} N_{ph}^2 L \frac{h_s}{3w_s} \end{aligned} \quad 11$$

And:

$$L_s = L_m + L_l \quad 12$$

For calculation of the stator resistance, the average length of one turn of the coil is required:

$$l_{av} = 2L + 4\tau_p \quad 13$$

where τ_p is the pole pitch. Then, the resistance will be:

$$R_s = \frac{\rho_{cu} N_{ph}^2 l_{av}}{q_1 A_s s_f p} \quad 14$$

Core, copper, and PM weights could be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{lam} &= \{2\pi \cdot r_r \cdot L_y + 2\pi r_s \cdot L_y + (\tau_s - w_s) l_s \cdot q_1 \cdot 2p \cdot m\} \cdot L \cdot \rho_{lam,m} \\ W_{cu} &= \{A_s \cdot l_{av} \cdot q_1 \cdot m \cdot p\} \cdot \rho_{cu,m} \\ W_{PM} &= \{2p \cdot l_m \cdot \tau_p \cdot \alpha\} \cdot L \cdot \rho_{PM,m} \\ W_{total} &= W_{lam} + W_{cu} + W_{PM} \end{aligned} \quad 15$$

where r_s and r_r are the mean stator and rotor yoke radii, respectively, and $\rho_{.,m}$ is the mass density.

And after calculation of the costs of materials used, the total cost will be:

$$C_{total} = C_{lam} + C_{PM} + C_{cu} \quad 16$$

The winding copper loss is:

$$P_{cu} = 3R_s I_{ph}^2 \quad 17$$

And the core loss is calculated by the loss density of the core as:

$$P_{fe} = \left\{ 2P_{fe0h} \cdot \frac{f}{50} \left(\frac{B_t}{1.5} \right)^2 + 2P_{fe0e} \left(\frac{f}{50} \right)^2 \left(\frac{B_t}{1.5} \right)^2 \right\} \times W_{lam} \quad 18$$

So, the efficiency is calculated as:

$$eff = \frac{P - P_{cu} - P_{fe}}{P} \quad 19$$

Finally, the stator heat dissipation area is:

$$A_c = 2\pi \left(r_s \pm \frac{l_y}{2} \right) L; \begin{cases} +: \text{inner rotor} \\ -: \text{outer rotor} \end{cases} \quad 20$$

And the temperature rise is:

$$\Delta T = \frac{(P_{cu} + P_{fe})}{A_c \cdot K_h} \quad 21$$

where K_h is the thermal convection coefficient.

To validate the analytical equations of previous section, a PMSG with the specifications and input parameters of Table 5 and Table 6 was simulated numerically in a finite element commercial software (Ansys Electronics Desktop). All material characteristics have been imported.

As shown in Figure 12, the magnetic flux density and temperature distribution in the core. As expected, the maximum flux density is about 1.8 T as defined in the initial parameters.

As shown in Figure 13a, the airgap flux density is about 0.78 T, and the no-load induced voltage is about 3% less than the desired value so, both are in good accordance with the analytical results. The small differences in the results are due to 3D effects that have not been included in the 2D analytical model.

The loading characteristics of currents and electrical and mechanical powers are shown in Figure 13b. Regarding the simulation, the analytical and numerical results are compared in Table 7 where it can be seen that the analytical model is verified.

Based on this model validation, the analytical model will be used in the next sections for the sensitivity analysis and design optimization as this model facilitates the optimization algorithm by reducing the time and memory required.

Parameter	Value	Description
P (kW)	2500	power
V_n (V)	3300	rated rms voltage
f (Hz)	25	frequency
n_s (rpm)	372	rated speed
p	4	pole pairs
m	3	phases
PM	VACODYM	permanent magnet
Core material	M700-65A	lamination

Table 5: PMSG specifications

Parameter	Value	Description
B_{rm}	1.2 T	PM remanence
μ_{rm}	1.1	PM relative permeability
B_t	1.8 T	tooth flux density
H_c	860000 A/m	magnetic coercivity
S_f	0.7	slot filling factor
P_{fe0h}	1.1	core loss hysteresis coefficient
P_{fe0e}	0.3	core loss eddy-current coefficient
k_h	60 W/m ² .°C	thermal convection coefficient
$C_{lam.}$	0.5 \$/kg	lamination cost
C_{PM}	95 \$/kg	PM cost
C_{cu}	5 \$/kg	copper cost
α	0.8	PM angle to pole ratio
q_1	5	slots per phase per pole
B_1	0.8 T	airgap flux density
J	4e6 A/m ²	current density
J_1	33e3 A/m	electric loading
g	15 mm	airgap length
r_g	500 mm	airgap mean radius

Table 6: base PMSG input parameters

Figure 12. loading simulation results, a) magnetic flux density in the core, b) temperature rise in stator

Figure 13: simulation results, a) no-load airgap flux density, b) no-load induced voltage, c) loading current, d) loading power

parameter	analytical	numerical
core loss	16 kW	14 kW
synchronous inductance	4.2 mH	4.5 mH
efficiency	98.6%	99%
temperature rise	79 °C	82 °C

Table 7: comparison of analytical and numerical results

4.2 Optimization Method

The model-based optimization was performed using the Genetic Algorithm (GA) to maximize the efficiency and minimize the weight, cost, and temperature rise subject to the constraints. The algorithm was configured to terminate if the discrepancy between the objective value in successive iterations drops below $1e - 2$ or if the algorithm completes 300 iterations, whichever condition is met first. The GA was chosen due to its efficiency in searching for the global optimum, handling both continuous and discrete variables, and managing to optimize multiple competing objectives in a multi-objective problem.

For the GA, the optimization variables and their ranges are selected as shown in Table 8. Minimizing objective function 5 would produce the best compromise between cost, temperature, weight, and efficiency. Based on this objective function, the optimal solution may not be equal to the optimal solution based on the other four objective functions, but it may be very close. Each term of objective function 5 can also be given a weighting factor to emphasize some more than others.

The optimization constraints are reported in Table 9. These constraints are selected for our application and could be modified as required.

To compare the optimization results, different objective functions have been defined as follows:

- Obj1: Minimize [total weight]
- Obj2: Minimize [total cost]
- Obj3: Minimize [temperature rise]
- Obj4: Maximize [efficiency]
- Obj5: Minimize [total weight × total cost × temperature rise ÷ efficiency]

The first 4 objective functions investigate a single characteristic and the last one combines 4 output characteristics to find the compromised solution as these characteristics are conflicted. As a result of the importance of cost-effectiveness, we have defined an objective function called "total cost" in our

optimization method. By using this objective function, we can design an economically advantageous wind turbine generator.

Minimizing objective function 5 would produce the best compromise between cost, temperature, weight, and efficiency. Based on this objective function, the optimal solution may not be equal to the optimal solution based on the other four objective functions, but it may be very close. Each term of objective function 5 can also be given a weighting factor to emphasize some more than others.

The optimization constraints are reported in Table 9. These constraints are selected for our application and could be modified as required.

parameter	min value	max value	type
α	0.6	0.8	Continuous
q_1	5	10	Discrete
B_1	0.7 T	0.9 T	Continuous
J	4e6 A/m ²	5e6 A/m ²	Continuous
J_1	30e3 A/m	50e3 A/m	Continuous
g	10 mm	20 mm	Continuous
r_g	200 mm	1000 mm	Continuous

Table 8: optimization variables

characteristic	constraint
$eff.$	> 94 %
C_{tot}	< 200 k\$
W_{tot}	< 12 ton
ΔT	< 500 °C

Table 9: optimization constraints

Figure 14 shows the optimized designs' characteristics for Obj1 to Obj4. Values are normalized with respect to the maximum value of each characteristic. It shows that for optimized temperature rise, the weight becomes the highest. For optimized weight, the cost also will be near the least. Temperature rise becomes the highest when cost is optimized. And for optimized efficiency, all other characteristics will be in the middle. The result trends for inner and outer rotor PMSGs are close to each other although there are differences in values. For better understanding in Figure 14, efficiency has been replaced with total loss since we will minimize all the objective functions.

Figure 14. comparison of optimized designs (for first 4 objective functions) in terms of output characteristics, a) inner rotor PMSG, b) outer rotor PMSG

Figure 15 compares the optimized designs of inner and outer PMSGs and the 4 output characteristics using the Obj5 function. It can be seen that the optimized inner rotor PMSG has slightly higher weight and cost, slightly lower loss but considerably lower temperature rise. This is due to the higher heat dissipation surface of the outer stator.

The optimal value of PM width to pole pitch and slot per pole per phase is 0.8 and 10, respectively, which are their maximum values. The optimal values of the airgap flux and airgap length also tend to their lower bounds. Different limits of these optimization variables will be set if there are no other restrictions.

Figure 15. comparison of Obj5 for inner and outer rotor PMSGs

4.3 Inner-rotor PMSG Optimized Designs

There are several output parameters that should be considered in the optimization such as total cost, total weight, efficiency, and temperature rise. As these parameters are conflict each other, the objective function could be defined by selecting any of these parameters individually, or as a combination of them (obj).

This section presents the optimization of the inner-rotor PMSG while different objective functions are considered. So, the visualized results make it easier to decide which output parameter would be of higher importance and interest to be optimized.

The cost of raw material is shown in Table 10. For each objective function, designs are sorted ascending or descending based on the prioritized parameter to show how other parameters change as getting away from the best design. In the following figures, the horizontal axis is the design number.

Material	Cost
lamination	2.5 \$/kg
PM	64 \$/kg
copper	8 \$/kg

Table 10: raw material cost

- Objective function: minimize total_cost

Figure 16. output parameters versus design number, sorted for cost

- Objective function: minimize total_weight

Figure 17. output parameters versus design number, sorted for weight

- Objective function: maximize efficiency

Figure 18. output parameters versus design number, sorted for efficiency

Once the material cost was determined, it was scaled by 1/0.632, as 63.2% is the average fraction of total cost of a finished product from materials and consumables for the energy industry sector [17].

As a case study, here the minimum cost design (#716) is presented in Table 11 and Table 12.

$q_1=11$	$r_g=840$ mm	$g=10$ mm	$J_1=54000$ A/m
$\alpha =0.84$	$B_g=0.6$ T	$J=5.2$ A/mm ²	

Table 11. best design’s parameters

efficiency= 97.7%	material weight= 6746 kg
temp. rise= 294 °C	outer diameter= 1.962 m
raw material cost= 39933 \$	axial length= 0.535 m
obj=1.228	

Table 12. output parameters

Between all designs:

- max obj. = 1.2571 for design #148
- max eff. = 98.4% for design #2129
- min weight = 6736.5 kg for design #1438
- min cost = 39933.3 \$ for design #716

As expected, the design reported in above tables has higher weight and lower efficiency compared to the best designs for weight and efficiency optimization.

The final generator cost is estimated at 64 k\$. It should be noted that other material usage such as shaft, supporting structures, and cooling system have not been considered in the final cost.

In addition, it should be noted that the results presented are the result of coarse optimization, and that finer improvements to the results could be achieved by modifying some of the initial parameters.

5 Thermal Management of the Generator

Heat transfer is one of the most important analyses for the generators. As the air ventilation is not proper for the nacelle's aerodynamic performance, a closed-loop water circulation and outside radiator system has been considered and studied.

Due to limitations in thermal analysis in Ansys electronics desktop, the flowing fluid has been represented by a thermal conductive material with equivalent conductivity that is calculated according to flow rate.

5.1 Equivalent Thermal Conductivity

Specific heat is the amount of thermal energy you need to supply to a sample weighing 1 kg to increase its temperature by 1 K. Specific heat capacity often varies with temperature, and is different for each state of matter. Liquid water has one of the highest specific heat capacities among common substances, about 4184 J/kg.°K at 20 °C.

$$Q = c \cdot m \cdot \Delta T \quad 22$$

where,

Q is in Jule, m in kg, T in K and c in (J/kg.°K).

Fourier's law of thermal conduction (also known as the law of heat conduction) states that the rate at which heat is transferred through a material is proportional to the negative of the temperature gradient and is also proportional to the area through which the heat flows.

The thermal conductivity of a material is described by the following formula:

$$k = \frac{q \cdot L}{A \cdot \Delta T} \quad 23$$

where,

k is the thermal conductivity in W/m.°K, q is the amount of heat transferred through the material in Joules/second or Watts, L is the distance between the two isothermal planes, A is the area of the surface in square meters, ΔT is the difference in temperature in Kelvin.

Figure 19 . thermal conductivity of a material

Using above two equations, the equivalent thermal conductivity could be calculated as a function of length and cross section area and flow rate of the liquid as:

$$k = \frac{\dot{m} \cdot c \cdot L}{A} \tag{24}$$

where, \dot{m} is the liquid’s flow rate (kg/s).

Assumptions in heat transfer analysis:

- The PMSG total electrical loss (watt) including the core and copper loss (71 kw) is modelled as a heat source in the stator core.
- This heat is transferred to the outside of nacelle through ducts attached to the outer surface of the stator which contain the circulating water, ducts parameter: length=1.5m, radius=2cm, number= 36. PMSG’s axial length is about 0.5m and the diameter is about 0.9m.
- The heat transfer capability of the circulating water is modelled by the equivalent thermal conductivity (eq. 24).
- Ducts transfer heat to the radiator to exchange to the ambient through convection (coefficient=150 w/m2. °K which requires some types of air-flowing equipment like fan). The radiator width and length are assumed to be as the PMSG diameter (~ 1.6m).

5.2 Simulation Results

The heat transfer and dissipation system including the heat source, ducts, radiator, and heat transfer coefficients were simulated in Ansys electronics desktop. The system configuration and simulation results are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 20. structure of cooling system

Figure 21. temperature distribution in PMSG

Using eq. (24), the required water flow rate is calculated to be 0.05 liter/s in the ducts.

This analysis shows that the cooling system can limit the maximum temperature inside the PMSG to 120 °K that is acceptable when considering the material characteristics.

6 3-MW Multi-Level DAB converter for Wireless Power Transfer System

The bidirectional Dual-Active-Bridge (DAB) is a power electronic structure used to interface high frequency transformer systems for energy conversion and it is used extensively in wireless power transfer system applications working at KHz-Frequency levels, (such as the RT windings). The DAB converter has become an attractive solution in electric vehicle, hybrid electric vehicle and high power-density aerospace applications because of its bidirectional power flow, galvanic isolation, high efficiency, and Zero-Voltage Switching (ZVS) [18], [19].

The three-phase DAB converter is generally considered in bi-directional applications since it has the advantages of the single-phase DAB converter such as soft switching capability without additional resonant components and smooth bidirectional power transition using a simple control structure. In addition, the 3P-DAB converter shows low conduction loss and high-power density because of its interleaved structure. The interleaved structure makes the “effective” switching frequency to increase, which can decrease the size of passive components and reduce the peak and root mean square (RMS) current [20]. Compared to single-phase DAB converter, three-phase DAB converter has higher power capability and lower ripple current on both the input and output side, which leads to lower capacitor volume and thus higher power density [18].

Unlike the single-phase counterpart, the three-phase structure can triple the effective frequency and reduce the amplitude of the ripple. Hence, input and output filters can be downsized; the transformer RMS current is also lower and power density is higher than that of the single-phase version [21].

The multi-level (ML) topologies of DAB converter offer several advantages. On one hand, for a given power rating and semiconductor technology, they allow operating at higher dc voltages, which allows increasing the conversion efficiency. On the other hand, for a given dc-link voltage rating, they allow operating with lower-voltage-rated devices with better performance features, reduce both switching and conduction losses, reduce the total harmonic distortion of voltage and current waveforms, and improve the converter fault-tolerance capacity.

ML topologies have three typical structures such as cascaded H-bridge (CHB), flying capacitor (FC), and neutral point clamped (NPC). The NPC is the simplest structure and the most suitable structure to apply to the DAB converter [22]. Among the existing ML topology families, the neutral point clamped (NPC) topologies

are the most promising in terms of efficiency, power density, and reliability [22]. NPC structure for three-level DAB converters is shown in Figure 22, where two diodes are added to each leg of one full bridge type to provide neutral point voltages.

The control parameter (ϕ) is defined as the phase shift between the fundamental components of primary voltage and the secondary voltage. Power flows from primary to secondary when the primary bridge leads the secondary by this angle. Reverse power flow is also possible with primary bridge lagging by ϕ [7].

The schematic of a 3-phase 3-level DAB DC/DC converter is shown in Figure 22 [20].

Figure 22. Circuit schematics of three-phase dual active bridge converter interfaced with the RT windings

Commercial application of multi-level converters has been limited up to medium voltage (MV) level (is generally considered within the range of 2.3 to 6.6kV) [23] due to unavailability of high-voltage and high-power semiconductor switches and diodes. The multi-level topologies have three typical structures such as cascaded H-bridge (CHB), flying capacitor (FC), and neutral point clamped (NPC). The CHB structure requires isolation between cascaded power supplies [24]. The FC structure needs to balance the flying capacitor voltage. However, the NPC structure is most commonly used as a simple structure without the above problems [23].

The modulation scheme proposed in this paper drives the high voltage bridge to generate a five-level voltage waveform while the other bridge generates a constant frequency 50% duty cycle square voltage waveform. The three-level primary voltage v_{ab} (from $0 < \theta \leq \pi$) has been assumed to be symmetrical around $\frac{\pi}{2}$. Due to this symmetry, only two variables α and β can be used to define the switching pattern of all the four switches in both the NPC legs. The other control parameter ϕ is defined as the phase shift between the fundamental components of primary five level voltage v_{ab} and the secondary two-level voltage v_{AB} . Power flows from primary to secondary when the primary bridge leads the secondary by an angle ϕ . Reverse power flow is also possible with primary bridge lagging by the angle ϕ [25].

The DAB topology can operate efficiently when the switching devices operate under zero voltage switching (ZVS) condition for the entire power range. This is achieved when the voltage conversion ratio d is equal to unity [25]. It is possible to achieve the same in the three-level DAB.

In the equations, $\omega = 2\pi f_s$ where f_s is the switching frequency, n is the transformer turns ratio, d is the voltage conversion ratio defined as $\frac{V_s}{nV_p}$ and L is total equivalent inductance between output and input bridge.

α and β are the switching angles for both couple switches S_{a2} and S_{a4} , and S_{a1} and S_{a3} simultaneously, respectively. The final power flow equations and the inductor current at time $t = 0$, are given here depending on the phase shift ϕ .

Case 1: $0 < \phi \leq \alpha$

$$i_L(0) = \frac{V_s}{n\omega L} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \phi \right) - \frac{V_p}{\omega L} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\alpha}{2} - \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \quad 25$$

$$P_o = \frac{V_p V_s}{n\omega L} \phi \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{\pi} - \frac{\beta}{\pi} \right) \quad 26$$

Case 2: $\alpha < \phi \leq \beta$

$$P_o = \frac{V_p V_s}{n\omega L} \left(\phi - \frac{\phi^2}{2\pi} - \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} - \frac{\alpha\beta}{\pi} \right) \quad 27$$

Case 3: $\beta < \phi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$

$$P_o = \frac{V_p V_s}{n\omega L} \left(\phi - \frac{\phi^2}{\pi} - \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} - \frac{\beta^2}{2\pi} \right) \quad 28$$

where i_L is the current flowing through L , and P_o is the output power.

In Case: 3, if the condition is such that $\alpha = \beta = 0$, the equation reduces to the conventional DAB converter as shown in [25]. The equations can be normalized to a base power ($P_{base} = \frac{V_p^2}{L\omega}$) and the normalized equation in per unit form for Case: 3 is given in (5).

$$P_o = d \left(\phi - \frac{\phi^2}{\pi} - \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} - \frac{\beta^2}{2\pi} \right), \quad \text{for Case 3} \quad 29$$

α , β , and ϕ are the angles that can be used to control the transfer power of the DAB converter. It should be noted that the primary and secondary voltages and inductor current would be identical in cases $\alpha < \beta$ and $\beta < \alpha$. By considering $\alpha = \beta = 0$, the maximum power would be transferred at $\phi = \pi/2$.

Capacitor voltage balancing is a critical issue for neutral-point-clamped-based converters. The unbalanced capacitor voltage will increase the voltage stress on power devices and negatively affect the reliability of the converters. Two typical problems during the capacitor voltage balancing process should be solved, i.e., power fluctuation minimization and determination of the transformer current polarity [26]. The capacitor voltage imbalance exists in the five-level control scheme, which can occur due to: 1) the tolerances in different power components, e.g., the dc-link capacitors and 2) synchronization failure of the gate-driving signals.

Under the voltage unbalanced condition, the voltage stress on power devices will increase, especially when the gate-driving signals fail to synchronize, which could exceed the voltage blocking capability and eventually damage the devices [21, 27]. Moreover, the capacitor voltage imbalance will affect the accuracy of the power transfer model of the DAB converters and affect the optimal operating conditions, e.g., efficiency [28].

Many solutions have been proposed for modulations with high switching-to-fundamental frequency ratios (m_f). However, such modulations would incur in high switching losses in the DAB converter, due to the HF nature of the DAB voltage and current fundamental components. Moreover, all the proposed DAB modulations in the literature feature $m_f = 1$ [29].

The principle of operation basically consists of controlling the charge being injected into/drawn from the inner dc-link points by modifying the modulation parameters [30-34] or by changing the switching sequence [24].

6.1 DAB Converter Design

Here, a 1 MW dual active bridge is designed to be used in the XROTOR project. The following parameters are used in the design process as stated in the previous section:

- Rated output power: 3 MW
- DC link voltage (V1 & V2): 5400 V

Therefore, the primary and secondary voltage has 2700 V peak value and:

- $\frac{V_p}{V_s} = \frac{5400}{5400} = 1, d = 1$
- Switching frequency: 2 kHz

In a converter with a 3MW power rating, the switches should be rated at 2700 V and 1.1 kA, assuming 5400 VDC on both primary and secondary sides. The following table also lists the industrial solutions that are available for this topology. Also, 2700 V diodes with 1.1 kA current rating would be required. Table 13 also lists the industrial solutions available in the market.

NO.	Mfr.	Mfr. Part No.	Configuration	Collector- Emitter Voltage V_{CE0}	Continuous Collector Current at 25°C	Pd - Power Dissipation	Temp.	Price
1	Infineon Technologies	FZ1400R33HE4BPSA1	2 IGBT+2 Diode	3300 V	1400 A	2.9 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,459.94
2	Infineon Technologies	FZ1600R33HE4BPSA1	2 IGBT+2 Diode	3300 V	1600 A	3.6 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,251.68
3	Infineon Technologies	FD1000R33HE3-K	2 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	1000 A	1.6 MW		£1,355.99
4	Infineon Technologies	FZ1500R33HL3	3 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	1500 A	2.4 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,951.36
5	Infineon Technologies	FZ2000R33HE4BOSA1	3 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	2000 A	4.2 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,940.48
6	Infineon Technologies	DD1000S33HE3	2 Diode	3300 V	1000 A	1.6 MW	-40 ~ +150	£926.55
7	Infineon Technologies	FZ1500R33HE3	3 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	1500 A	2.4 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,492.24
8	Infineon Technologies	FZ1000R33HE3	2 IGBT+2 Diode	3300 V	1000 A	Not mentioned	-40 ~ +150	£1,374.80
9	Infineon Technologies	FZ1000R33HL3	2 IGBT+2 Diode	3300 V	1000 A	Not mentioned	-50 ~ +150	£1,486.42
10	Infineon Technologies	FZ1200R33HE3	3 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	1200 A	1.8 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,419.29
11	Infineon Technologies	FD1000R33HL3-K	2 IGBT+3 Diode	3300 V	1000 A	1.6 MW	-40 ~ +150	£1,725.45

Table 13. Available switches for the target converter

6.2 Implementation in Simulink

A three-phase multi-level dual active bridge DC/DC converter is simulated using MATLAB/Simulink, as shown in Figure 23. This circuit consists of two DC voltage source with 5400 V rating. Two three-phase full-bridge converters are connected to each other through inductors and a three-phase transformer with YY connection. To keep the input and output voltages stable, capacitors are considered in parallel with the input and output as shown in Figure 22. The dead-time is 0.1 microseconds.

To cancel the reactive power required by the RT in the DAB converter, a series connected capacitor is placed in the input of the transformer. The RT parameters calculated in Section 2 are used here to integrate the rotary transformer with the DAB converter.

The on-state resistance for the above switch is calculated and equals 0.375 mΩ. This parameter is included in the simulations. The forward-bias resistance of the diode is calculated in the same way, and it is equal to 0.035 mΩ.

The simulation parameters are listed in Appendix.

Figure 23. The simulation environment in Simulink

Figure 24. Three-phase ML DAB converter with rotary transformer simulation in Simulink.

Figure 25. Gate pulse generation for DAB converter switches

Figure 37. ML-DAB converter switching pattern

Figure 26. The switch driver pulses

6.3 Simulation Results considering Power Electronics Loss

The IGBTs losses are computed as follows:

Turn-on loss: Pre-switching value of the voltage across the device, post-switching value of the current flowing into the device, and the junction temperature are used to determine the energy losses with the help of a 3D lookup table, i.e. $E_{ON} = f(I_C, T)$ where I_C is the current and T is the temperature. This energy is converted into a power pulse which is injected into the thermal network.

Turn-off loss: Pre-switching value of the current flowing into the device, post-switching value of the voltage across the device, and the junction temperature are used to determine the energy losses with the help of a 3D lookup table, i.e. $E_{OFF} = f(I_C, T)$. This energy is converted into a power pulse which is injected into the thermal network.

Conduction loss: the current (I_C) flowing in the device and its junction temperature (T) determine what would be the saturation voltage (V_{CE}) across the IGBT using a 2D look-up table, i.e. $I_C = f(V_{CE}, T)$. This is then multiplied by current to obtain the losses which are injected into the thermal network.

The diode's losses are computed as follows:

Reverse recovery loss: Pre-switching value of the current (I_f) flowing into the device, post switching value of the voltage (V_f) across the device, and the junction temperature (T) are used to determine the energy losses with the help of a 3-D lookup table, i.e. $E = f(I_f, V_f, T)$. This energy is converted into a power pulse which is injected into the thermal network.

Conduction loss: the current (I_f) flowing in the device and its junction temperature determine what the on-state voltage (V_f) across the diode would be using a 2D look-up table, i.e. $V_f = f(I_f, T)$. This is then multiplied by current to obtain the losses which are injected into the thermal network.

The output of the electrical model, which is the total power loss of the device, is fed into the thermal model. The thermal model uses this value of power loss to calculate the temperature of the components present in the thermal model.

The temperature rise for both input and output side converters has been simulated and the results are shown in Figure 27. The input power (top), output power (middle) and the efficiency (bottom) versus time(s)By

considering 40°C for the ambient temperature, the heat sink temperature will rise to 70 °C and 105 °C for the input and output converters, respectively.

Figure 27. The input power (top), output power (middle) and the efficiency (bottom) versus time(s)

Figure 28. Phase-phase voltages in the rotary transformer primary side.

Figure 29. Three phase currents in the rotary transformer primary side

Figure 30. The simulation results for the DC link voltages, inductor current, secondary side DC current, phase shift angle and the output power

Figure 31. The primary (blue) and secondary (yellow) heatsink temperature (°C)

Another important challenge regarding the use of DAB converters and rotary transformer is the power loss and their efficiency. The input power, output power and the overall efficiency are depicted in Figure 27, respectively. As seen in this figure, the overall efficiency in the nominal power of 3MW is about 96%.

7 Control System Design for the Powertrain

One of the most important aspects of the XROTOR is how to control the power flow and inject power to the grid while control objectives are met. Each tower consists of two PMSG and two wireless power transfer system. The aim of this section is to analyse the control strategy and how it is possible to avoid over rating of the converters.

This section connects the DAB converters in parallel to balance power sharing, reduce power oscillations and avoid over-rating owing to the XROTOR structure and phase shift between the mechanical torques acting on the two generators. In addition, each DAB converter has a rotary transformer to enable wireless power transmission and eliminate the need for slip rings. By using this wireless power transfer instead of slip rings, operation and maintenance costs would be reduced. Finally, grid side DC/AC converters are considered to

deliver power to the network from each generator. Accordingly, each generator requires three controllers to be properly controlled.

7.1 Basics of the Control Approach

To simulate the power train, all elements of the system should be modelled by their electrical and mathematical representations. For the modelling of the different elements, the *DQ0* transformation is extensively used for both system models and controllers. The characteristics of the transformation are presented first, and the modelling continue afterwards.

7.1.1 The *dq0* transformation

It is well-known that for a PI or IMC controllers, zero steady state error between the set point and the steady state signal is achieved as long as set point and the signal-to-control are DC quantities in steady state. However, the AC currents quantities in both machine and grid side converters are in this case a set 3 sinusoidal signals, PI controllers are incapable to regulate these currents without a steady state phase error. To alleviate this problem, a mathematical transformation that converts 3 phase AC quantities into 3 DC quantities is used. This transformation converts a three-phase time-domain signal from a stationary coordinate system, *abc*, to a rotating coordinate system of two orthogonal phases *d*, *q* and a zero-sequence component. The *q* axis of the *dq0* coordinate system is chosen to be lagging the *d* axis by 90 degrees. The angular speed of the *dq0* rotating coordinate system can be chosen to match the synchronous speed of the AC grid; this allows to mathematically “see” any AC voltage or current space vector that is rotating at the same angular speed to that of the *dq0* frame as a constant spatial distribution [35]. Hence, any balanced three-phase ac space vector quantities can be transformed to two DC quantities (resulting from the projection of the ac space vector in the *d* and *q* axis) and a zero-sequence component. Figure 32 shows the geometric derivation of the *dq0* transformation applied to the three-phase waveform where θ_{dq} is the angle between the *d* axis of the rotating frame and phase *a* of the three phase system, ω_s is the angular speed of the three-phase system and ω_{dq} is the angular speed of the *dq0* rotating frame.

Figure 32: Geometric Derivation of the *dq0* Transformation applied to a 3-Phase System

The $dq0$ transformation is performed to the grid voltages by applying the following transformation the 3-phase sinusoidal signal:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_d \\ X_q \\ X_0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_{dq} & \cos(\theta_{dq} - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(\theta_{dq} + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ -\sin \theta_{dq} & -\sin(\theta_{dq} - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & -\sin(\theta_{dq} + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_a \\ X_b \\ X_c \end{bmatrix} \quad 30$$

where X_d , X_q and X_0 are the d, q and 0 representation of the sinusoidal signals, X_a , X_b and X_c are the a, b and c sinusoidal components (it can be voltages, currents, fluxes, inductance matrixes etc) and the rotary frame angle θ_{dq} is a function of rotary frame angular speed ω_{dq} and of an initial value $\theta_{dq}(0)$:

$$\theta_{dq} = \int_0^t \omega_{dq}(t) dt + \theta_{dq}(0) \quad 31$$

The calculation of the $dq0$ quantities in all systems of the drivetrain, including the ABC dynamic models make use of equation 30 to deal with DC signals instead of AC signals, this makes the modelling computationally efficient and the controller deployment an easier task.

Given the type of connection of a power electronic converter and the generator or a grid source, the zero-sequence voltages and currents are zero by physical constraints, no matter if the phases are balanced or not. As such, the $dq0$ representation of the grid voltages and currents can be reduced to a dq without losing information. Because of this, the zero-sequence representation of the voltage and currents are disregarded for controller design purposes.

In the case of the grid side elements, if in the $dq0$ ω_{dq} is selected to be the same of as the AC grid angle (i.e. $\omega_{dq} = \omega_s$) then the transformation will be synchronized with the AC grid and the $dq0$ of the AC grid voltages and currents values will become DC quantities, as such PI or IMC controllers can be used to generate fast and robust controllers able to control the magnitude and phase of the 3 phase AC system with zero steady state error. The same can be said for a transformation synchronized with the generator electrical angle (i.e. $\omega_{dq} = \omega_r$) for the machine side elements.

In order to synchronize the $dq0$ transformation with the AC grid, a system that provides the transformation with the grid angular speed ω_s is required. This is the task of the Phase Lock Loop (PLL).

The PLL A phase-locked loop or phase lock loop (PLL) is a control system that generates an output signal whose phase is related to the phase of an input signal. A useful analogy for the PLL behaviour consists of a servo motor that tries to catch a rotating mass. The angle provided by the PLL output is synchronized with the positive sequence of the filtered grid voltage. The PLL measures the alpha and beta components of the voltage and translates them to the dq -reference frame. If the dq -frame is fully aligned with the alpha component, the angle of the voltage vector should be ideally zero. If the dq -frame is not fully aligned there is an error, and the angle of the voltage vector in the dq -reference frame will not be zero. The closed loop control will try to increase/decrease the reference frame angular speed to make that angle null. For this aim, the PLL passes the angle error through a PI controller. The output of this PI controller is the angular speed (frequency) of the rotating dq -reference frame. The phase of the dq -reference frame is obtained by using an integrator (a VCO in a traditional PLL) for the previous frequency. The PLL used in this research is the well-known robust SOGI PLL [36].

7.1.2 Generator Model and Control

The model of the generator in ABC frame is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
v_{as} &= i_{as}r_{as} + \frac{d}{dt}\psi_{as} \\
v_{bs} &= i_{as}r_{bs} + \frac{d}{dt}\psi_{bs} \\
v_{cs} &= i_{as}r_{cs} + \frac{d}{dt}\psi_{cs} \\
\psi_{PM} &= i_f L_f
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where $v_{as}, v_{bs}, v_{cs}, i_{as}, i_{bs}, i_{cs}, r_{as}, r_{bs}, r_{cs}, L_{aa}, L_{bb}, L_{cc}, \psi_{as}, \psi_{bs}, \psi_{cs}$ are the voltage, resistance, current self inductances and fluxes stator a, b, c phases, respectively. ψ_{PM} is the PM flux, i_f is the equivalent rotor current and L_f is the equivalent rotor inductance.

The generator can be modelled in the rotor reference frame (dq) as:

$$\begin{aligned}
v_{ds} &= r_s i_d + L_d \frac{di_d}{dt} - \omega_e L_q i_q \\
v_{qs} &= r_s i_q + L_q \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_e L_d i_d + \lambda \omega_e \\
T_e &= \frac{3}{2} p [\psi_{PM} i_q + (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q]
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Where i_d, i_q are d-axis and q-axis currents, v_{ds}, v_{qs} are d-axis and q-axis stator voltages, L_d, L_q are d-axis and q-axis inductances, R_s is resistance, ω_e is electrical speed of the rotor, p is the pole pairs

If the D-axis stator current of the generator is commanded to be zero, then a linear relationship between the stator Q current and the Electromechanical torque is obtained.

$$T_e = T_e = \frac{3}{2} p [\psi_{PM} i_q + (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q] + \left(\frac{3p}{2}\right) i_{qs} \psi'_{PM} = \left(\frac{3p}{2}\right) i_{qs} \psi_{PM} \tag{34}$$

The DQ equations of the Voltages of the PMSG can be used directly to define the transfer functions that relate Stator Voltages with Stator Currents, this is:

$$\begin{aligned}
m_{ds} \left(\frac{v_{dc}}{2}\right) &= v_{ds} = r_s i_{ds} + L_d \frac{d}{dt} i_{ds} - \omega_r L_q i_{qs} \\
m_{qs} \left(\frac{v_{dc}}{2}\right) &= v_{qs} = r_s i_{qs} + L_q \frac{d}{dt} i_{qs} + \omega_r L_d i_{ds} + \omega_r \psi_{PM}
\end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Where m_{ds} and m_{qs} are the modulator signals to be fed to the generator side converter, which will in turn convert them to the v_{ds}, v_{qs} stator voltages that will be fed to the generator.

If the cross-coupling terms are ignored, then the transfer functions to control the stator currents by means of modulator signals are given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{i_{ds}(s)}{m_{ds}(s)} &= P_{sd}(s) = \frac{\frac{v_{dc}}{2}}{L_d s + r} \\
\frac{i_{qs}(s)}{m_{qs}(s)} &= P_{sq}(s) = \frac{\frac{v_{dc}}{2}}{L_q s + r}
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Since both equations are first order systems, a simple PI controller configured to perform pole-zero cancellation technique can provide an acceptable first order response in the closed loop controller. As such if the proportional and integral constants of the controllers are selected as $Kp = \alpha L_d / (\frac{v_{dc}}{2})$, and $Ki =$

$\alpha r_s / (\frac{v_{dc}}{2})$, then a closed loop response time from reference to output (t_{r_G}) will be dictated by the bandwidth α , which is related the rise time of the closed loop response as:

$$\alpha \approx \frac{0.35}{t_{r_G}} \text{ (Hz) or } \alpha \approx \frac{2.2}{t_{r_G}} \text{ (rad)} \tag{37}$$

A schematic diagram of the current controller for the PMSG is shown in Figure 33. The schematic evidence that a desired electrical torque can be obtained by commanding the q stator current, since there is a linear relationship between the two. However, to control the speed of the PMSG an outer control loop needs to be connected to the electrical torque reference.

Figure 33. Schematic diagram of the PMSG current controller.

The speed dynamics of a PMSG wind turbines are govern by the mechanical system of the turbine, is defined as:

$$J \frac{d}{dt} \omega_m = T_e - T_{mech} - D \omega_m \tag{38}$$

where J is the inertia of the rotor body, ω_m is the mechanical speed of the generator, T_{mech} is the mechanical torque and D is regarded as the viscous damping. Using the Laplace transform the following transfer function for the rotor speed dynamics can be obtained:

$$\frac{\omega_m(s)}{T_e(s) - T_{mech}(s)} = \frac{1}{Js + D} \tag{39}$$

Looking the equation, it is evident that if T_{mech} is considered a disturbance, then the speed of the PMSG can be controlled with a T_e input.

$$\frac{\omega_m(s)}{T_e(s)} = \frac{1}{Js + D} \tag{40}$$

Just as in the case of the current controller, this first order transfer function that can be controlled using the pole-zero cancellation technique. If the proportional and integral constants are calculated as $K_p = \alpha_m J$ and $K_i = \alpha_m D$ then the closed loop response time from reference to output will be dictated by the bandwidth α_m , which is related the rise time of the closed loop response.

The pole-zero cancellation tuning rules for the speed controller assume it is possible to generate whatever command of $T_e(s)$ instantaneously. In reality, the generation of an electromagnetic Torque Reference involves the closed loop dynamics of PMSG stator current controller. However, if the speed of response of the current control loops are at least 10 times faster than the speed controller loops, then we can separate dynamics and use the nested control approach. A schematic representation of the nested control approach is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34 Schematic diagram of nested control topology for speed control of the PMSG.

The full diagram of the PMSG speed controller is show in Figure 35.

Figure 35. Full speed control structure of the PMSG.

7.1.3 Internal Model Control

The internal model control (IMC) technique relies on the “internal model” principle whose philosophy states that a control action over a plant can be achieved only if the control system includes, either implicitly or explicitly, some representation of the process to be controlled [37, 38]. Figure 36 show the structure of the IMC.

Figure 36. IMC Controller Structure.

As seen in Figure 36, the model of the plant to be controlled ($G'(s)$) is to be an exact representation of the plant itself ($G(s)$) and considering that no disturbance is present, then the estimated effect of disturbance $d'(s)$, resulting from the difference between the plant output and the plant model output, turns zero and the close loop system turns equal to the open loop system. On this condition, an IMC controller of the type $B(s) = G'^{-1}(s)$ implies a perfect theoretical control then. However, such ideal control cannot be implemented by two main reasons,

- The need of use pure differentiators, (in case the model of the plant is proper)
- Infinitely large excursions of the manipulative variable for infinitely small high frequency disturbances (which cannot be implemented realistically in any digital or analogue controller).

For a realizable control, the IMC structure introduces a low pass filter $L(s)$ in cascade to the IMC controller. The filter is designed to add poles to $G(s)$ in order to turn the controller transfer function proper.

The filter $L(s)$ is usually of the type:

$$L(s) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{s + \alpha}\right)^n \tag{41}$$

Where the order of the filter, n , is chosen accordingly to the order of $G(s)$, and α is regarded as the closed loop bandwidth of the filter, for a first order filter.

The IMC controller has the advantage of having the controller parameters related in a unique, straightforward manner to the model parameters with α being the only controller variable to be adjusted.

With respect to the plant output, the closed loop system acts on the reference input as a low pass filter. However, with respect to the plant input, the closed loop system acts on the disturbance input as a high pass filter. The smoothness of the transient response at the plant output in the former case and at the plant input in the latter case, is related to the closed loop system damping. If this damping is low, the transient responses can be quite oscillatory. With regard to the plant output, the plant acts, additionally to the feedback back system, on the disturbance input as a low pass filter. Knowing that some of the plants to control in the power train are extremely susceptible to disturbances (For example, all the DC voltage plants in the drivetrain system), an inner feedback loop to R can be added to provide an additional degree of control freedom to speed up the load disturbance rejection of a poorly damped plant. This additional control loop is used to speed up the natural response of the plant by moving the pole of the plant away from the origin within the negative side of the real axis. The configuration of the additional control loop is shown in Figure 37.

By adding a feedback loop the transfer function of the improved plant $M(s)$ turns to be:

$$M(s) = \frac{G(s)}{1 + G(s)R} = \frac{1}{G^{-1}(s) + R} \tag{42}$$

where $M(s)$ is the new transfer function of the plant augmented with an inner feedback loop gain R .

Figure 37: The Two Degrees of Freedom IMC Configured as a PI Controller

This IMC with two degrees of freedom is especially useful for the poorly damped systems of the inverter such as the DC circuit.

The processes to be controlled using the two degrees of freedom IMC controller are the d q currents and the DC voltage. The transfer functions of these processes are given by a first order transfer function, implying a first-degree filter for their respective IMC controller. Under this consideration the transfer function of the IMC control $F(s)$ (considering that $M'(s)$ is the model of $M(s)$) is shown in 43.

$$F(s) = \frac{B(s)}{1-B(s)M'(s)} = \frac{L(s)M'^{-1}(s)}{1-L(s)M'^{-1}(s)M'(s)} = \frac{\alpha}{s} M'^{-1}(s) \quad 43$$

The additional degree of freedom is chosen, in each case controller case, to make the process dynamics as fast as the controller dynamics. This allows the load disturbance rejection to be as fast as the controllers closed loop dynamics. To achieve this, the pole R is set in the inner feedback loop to match the pole of the IMC controller in the transfer function from the disturbance $d(s)$ to output signal of the plant $y(s)$, which is (assuming $M'(s) = M(s)$):

$$\frac{y(s)}{d(s)} = \frac{M(s)}{1+F(s)M(s)} = \frac{M(s)}{1+(\alpha/s)M^{-1}(s)M(s)} = \left(\frac{s}{s+\alpha}\right) \frac{1}{G^{-1}(s)+R} \quad 44$$

If R is chosen appropriately, can be reduced to:

$$\frac{y(s)}{d(s)} = \left[\left(\frac{s}{s+\alpha}\right) \frac{K}{s+\alpha}\right] = K \left[\frac{s}{(s+\alpha)^2}\right] \quad 45$$

where K is a constant.

As can be notice in 45 now the transfer function from the disturbance to the output of the plant shares the same time constant load disturbance $d(s)$ is damped with the same time constant as the closed loop control. The IMC controller closed loop bandwidth α is chosen accordingly the rise time t_r needed for the output signal $y(s)$.

To illustrate the advantages of using the two degrees of freedom IMC Figure 38 shows a simulation result where a first order plant is controlled by a PI using technical optimum (pole-zero matching) and the same plant is controlled using an IMC controller. Both controllers are exposed at a set-point change at $t=0.1$ and then to a disturbance at $t=0.2$. As seen in Figure 38 both the PI controller and the IMC controller respond with the same dynamics for a set point change, however a much better transient response (in terms of overshoot and settling time) is provided by the 2 degrees of freedom IMC during a disturbance.

Figure 38: IMC and PI Controller Transient Response Comparison for a First Order Plant

7.1.4 D and Q Current Control

The equations defining the behaviour of the currents between the grid-side converter and its respective ac grid, expressed in dq components is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_{d_gsc} &= r i_{d_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{d_gsc} - \omega_s L i_{q_gsc} - v_{d_g} \\
 v_{q_gsc} &= r i_{q_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{q_gsc} + \omega_s L i_{d_gsc} - v_{q_g}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{46}$$

where r and L are, respectively, the equivalent resistance and inductance between the GSC and the grid, v_{d_gsc} and v_{q_gsc} are the dq components of the average voltages generated by the grid side converter.

The transfer functions used to control the dq inverter currents can be reduced to a similar expression if the cross-coupling terms ($\omega_s L i_{q_gsc}$ and $\omega_s L i_{d_gsc}$), and the grid voltage components, (v_{d_g} and v_{q_g}) from equation (46) are considered disturbances, not present during the calculation of the dq current control, instead being numerically compensated. Hence, the GSC current-to-voltage relationships in the dq frame are:

$$\frac{i_{d_gsc}(s)}{v_{d_gsc}(s)} = \frac{i_{q_gsc}(s)}{v_{q_gsc}(s)} = \frac{i(s)}{v_{gsc}(s)} = G_i(s) = \frac{1}{Ls + r}
 \tag{47}$$

If an inner feedback loop of gain R_i is added to the inverter current plant to add active damping to G_i (i.e a second degree of freedom as shown in equation (42) a transfer function of the following type is obtained:

$$M_i(s) = \frac{1}{R_i + Ls + r}
 \tag{48}$$

The inner feedback loop is implemented to the plant by means of making the input signal to the plant equal to:

$$v_{gsc}(s) = v'_{gsc}(s) - i(s)R_i
 \tag{49}$$

where $v'(s)$ is the output of the IMC current controller $F_i(s)$, which, accordingly to equation (43) turns to be:

$$F_i(s) = \alpha_i L + \frac{(r+R_i)\alpha_i}{s}
 \tag{50}$$

where α_i is the bandwidth of the closed loop system of dq current control system.

from (50) we can deduce the controller constants as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Kp_i &= \alpha_i L \\
 Ki_i &= (r + R_i)\alpha_i
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{51}$$

Now, we can select R_i to match the pole of $M_i(s)$ with the pole of $F_i(s)$ on the transfer function from the disturbance $d_i(s)$ to the output of the plant $i(s)$, as described in equation (45). Thus, selecting R_i to have the value of:

$$R_i = \alpha_i L - r
 \tag{52}$$

It is possible to prove that the relationship $v_{inv}(s)/d_i(s)$ turns to be:

$$\frac{v_{gsc}(s)}{d_i(s)} = \frac{s}{L(\alpha_i + s)^2}
 \tag{53}$$

As seen in equation 53 the disturbances coming from $d_i(s)$ are rejected by the plant and the controller with the same time constant, which in turn depends on α_i . Figure 39 shows the inverter current control loop.

Figure 39: Inverter Currents Control Loop

Figure 40 shows the digital implementation of the IMC current controller.

Figure 40: Digital Implementation of IMC Current Controller

7.1.5 Direct Voltage Controller

The DC plant equation of the grid side converter is defined as:

$$C \frac{dv_{dc}}{dt} = i_{dc_load} + i_{dc} \quad 54$$

where i_{dc_load} is the dc current absorbed by the load or the DC network connected to dc side of the inverter i_{dc} is the DC current of the inverter and C is full equivalent capacitance of the DC circuit. The average value of i_{dc} can be represented in term of the ac currents and modulator signals. In dq reference frame this is:

$$i_{dc} = \frac{3}{4} (m_{d_gsc} i_{d_gsc} + m_{q_gsc} i_{q_gsc}) \quad 55$$

where m_{d_gsc} and m_{q_gsc} are the d and q components of the grid side converter modulator signal. The equation of the ac circuit of the GSC, in terms of modulator signals is thus given by [39]:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{v_{dc}}{2} m_{d_gsc} = v_{d_gsc} &= r i_{d_gsc} + L \frac{di_{d_gsc}}{dt} - L \omega i_{q_gsc} - v_{d_g} \\ \frac{v_{dc}}{2} m_{q_gsc} = v_{q_gsc} &= r i_{q_gsc} + L \frac{di_{q_gsc}}{dt} + L \omega i_{d_gsc} - v_{q_g} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad 56$$

Substituting equation 55 and equation 56 in equation 54 and assuming the grid voltage is aligned to v_{d_g} (i.e. $v_{q_g} = 0$) the following expressions for i_{dc} and the inverter dc power P_{dc} are obtained:

$$i_{dc} = \frac{3r}{2v_{dc}} (i_{d_gsc}^2 + i_{q_gsc}^2) + \frac{3L}{2v_{dc}} \left(i_{d_gsc} \frac{di_{d_gsc}}{dt} + i_{q_gsc} \frac{di_{q_gsc}}{dt} \right) - \frac{3}{2v_{dc}} (v_{d_g} i_{d_gsc}) \quad 57$$

$$i_{dc} v_{dc} = P_{dc} = \frac{3R}{2} (i_{d_gsc}^2 + i_{q_gsc}^2) + \frac{3L}{4} \frac{d}{dt} (i_{d_gsc}^2 + i_{q_gsc}^2) - \frac{3}{2} (v_{d_g} i_{d_gsc}) \quad 58$$

Equation 58 shows that the dc side power of the inverter is composed by the sum of the resistive losses in the ac side ($3(i_{d_gsc}^2 + i_{q_gsc}^2)r/2$) plus the energy stored in the inductance between the GSC and the AC grid ($\frac{3L}{4} \frac{d}{dt} (i_{d_gsc}^2 + i_{q_gsc}^2)$) plus the AC active power ($\frac{3}{2} (v_{d_g} i_{d_gsc})$).

Since the resistive losses are very small, they can be neglected from the dynamic equation of P_{dc} , also for low values of L the energy stored in the inductance can be neglected too. Thus, the equation describing the dynamics of the DC voltage can be simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} C v_{dc} \frac{dv_{dc}}{dt} &= v_{dc} (i_{dc_load} + i_{dc}) \rightarrow \\ C v_{dc} \frac{dv_{dc}}{dt} &= P_{load} + P_{dc} \rightarrow \\ \frac{C}{2} \frac{dv_{dc}^2}{dt} &= P_{load} + \left(-\frac{3}{2} (v_{d_gsc} i_{d_gsc}) \right) \end{aligned} \quad 59$$

In order to work with linear expressions (assuming v_{d_gsc} is constant), the output variable of the DC-plant is selected to be the square of the capacitor voltage (i.e. a representation of the energy of the capacitor). Thus, selecting the square of the capacitor voltage to be $w = v_{dc}^2$ and considering P_{load} a disturbance, not present during the calculation of the voltage controller, the transfer function of the dc-plant can be presented as:

$$-\frac{w(s)}{i_{d_gsc}(s)} = -G_w(s) = -\frac{3v_{d_gsc}}{Cs} \tag{60}$$

As seen in equation 60 $-G_{dc}(s)$ has a pole in the origin, which makes it very susceptible to disturbances.

Following the procedure for designing a two degree of freedom IMC controller, an inner feedback loop of gain R_w is added to the DC-plant to add active damping to G_w (i.e a second degree of freedom as shown in equation (42)). This is:

$$-M_w(s) = -\frac{G_w(s)}{1+G_w(s)R_w} = -\frac{3v_{d_g}}{Cs+3v_{d_g}R_w} \tag{61}$$

The inner feedback loop is implemented to the DC-plant by means of making the input signal to the dc-plant equal to:

$$i_{d_gsc}(s) = i_{d_gsc}'(s) - w(s)R_w \tag{62}$$

where $i_{d_gsc}'(s)$ is the output of the IMC current controller $F_w(s)$, which, accordingly to equation 43 turns to be:

$$F_w(s) = \frac{\alpha_w}{s} (-)M_w^{-1}(s) = \frac{\alpha_w}{s} \left(-\frac{3v_{d_gsc}}{Cs+3v_{d_gsc}R_w} \right)^{-1} = -\left(\frac{\alpha_w C}{3v_{d_gsc}} + \frac{\alpha_w R_w}{s} \right) \tag{63}$$

where α_w is the bandwidth of the closed loop system of the $v_{dc}^2 = w$ control system.

From equation (63) the controller constants can be calculated as:

$$Kp_w = \frac{\alpha_w C}{3v_{d_gsc}} \tag{64}$$

$$Ki_w = \alpha_w R_w$$

Now, R_w can be selected to match the pole of $M_w(s)$ with the pole of $F_w(s)$ on the transfer function from the disturbance $d_w(s)$ (in this case P_{load}) to the output of the plant $w(s)$. The process to do this is presented in equation (45). Thus, selecting R_{dc} to have the value of:

$$R_{dc} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\alpha_{dc} C}{v_{d_gsc}} \tag{65}$$

it can be shown that the relationship v_{dc}^2/P_{load} turns to:

$$\left(\frac{v_{dc}^2(s)}{P_{load}} \right) = \left(\frac{2s}{(Cs + 3v_{d_gsc}G_{dc})(s + \alpha_{dc})} \right) = \left(\frac{2s}{C(s + \alpha_{dc})^2} \right) \tag{66}$$

As seen in equation (66) a power step of magnitude $|P_{load}|$ is rejected by the dc plant with the same time constant of closed loop controller, which in turn depends on α_w . Figure 41 shows the DC voltage control loop.

Figure 41: DC Voltage Control Loop

Figure 42 shows the digital implementation of the IMC controller.

Figure 42: Digital Implementation of DC Voltage Controller

7.1.6 Reactive Power Control

The apparent power of a 3 phase AC system, S , in terms of dq voltages and currents is defined as:

$$S = \frac{3}{2}(v_{dqg})(i_{dqgsc})^* = \frac{3}{2}(v_{dg} + jv_{qg})(i_{d_gsc} - ji_{q_gsc}) \tag{67}$$

$$= \frac{3}{2}(v_{d_g}i_{d_gsc} + v_{q_g}i_{q_gsc}) + j(v_{q_g}i_{d_gsc} - v_{d_g}i_{q_gsc}) = P + jQ$$

where P is the active power and Q is the reactive power. If the d axis of the $dq0$ rotatory frame is assumed to be aligned with the ac space vector, then the voltage representation in dq consist only of d components (i.e. $\omega_{dq} = \omega_s$, $v_{d_g} = v_{grid}$ and $v_{q_g} = 0$) as seen in Figure 43. In this case, equation 67 can be simplified to:

$$P = \frac{3}{2}v_{d_g}i_{d_gsc} \tag{68}$$

$$Q = -\frac{3}{2}v_{d_g}i_{q_gsc}$$

Figure 43. $dq0$ Transformation of the Grid Voltages when the d Axis is aligned to the AC Space Vector

According to equation 68 the relationship between the amount of q current and the inverter reactive power is directly proportional if the ac voltage is assumed to be a constant value. Because of this, a simple integral

controller is enough to control the reactive power with first order dynamics and 0 steady state error. The transfer function, G_Q , from the reactive power Q to the i_q current is given by:

$$G_Q = \frac{i_{q_gsc}}{Q} = -\frac{2}{3v_{d_g}} \tag{69}$$

If an integral controller of the type $C_Q(s) = Ki_Q/s$, (where Ki_Q is the integral constant of the reactive power controller) is added in cascade with G_Q the following open loop expression is obtained:

$$A_Q(s) = G_Q \cdot C_Q(s) = -\frac{2Ki_Q}{3v_{d_g}s} \tag{70}$$

If Ki_Q is selected to have a value of $Ki_Q = -3v_{d_gsc}\alpha_Q/2$, where α_Q can be regarded as the closed loop bandwidth of the controller, then the open loop expression $A_Q(s)$ and the closed loop expression $E_Q(s)$ from the reactive power reference Q_{ref} to Q are:

$$A_Q(s) = -\frac{2}{3v_{d_g}} \left(-\frac{3v_{d_g}\alpha_Q}{2} \right) = \frac{\alpha_Q}{s} \tag{71}$$

$$E_P(s) = \frac{Q}{Q_{ref}} = \frac{A_Q(s)}{1+A_Q(s)} = \frac{\alpha_Q}{s+\alpha_Q}$$

As seen in equation 71 the closed loop dynamics of the active power control loop are first order with a closed loop bandwidth of α_Q . The value of α_Q can be selected for a given rise time of the control variable by following the formula that defines the relationship between bandwidth and rise time in first order systems. Figure 44 shows the block diagram of the reactive power control loop.

Figure 44. Schematic Diagram of the Reactive Power Control Loop

Figure 45 shows the digital implementation of the reactive power controller.

Figure 45. Digital Implementation of the Reactive Power Controller

The step response and bode plots of the reactive power closed loop control system for a bandwidth of $\alpha_Q = 220$ rad. ($t_{r_Q} = 0.01$ sec) is show in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Step response and bode plot of the closed loop reactive power controller.

7.1.7 Cross Coupling Term Elimination

The cross-coupling elimination allows the independent control of the d and q currents by eliminating the terms that link the two currents in the equations of the voltage of the GSC. In order to do this, the following terms are added to the voltage control signals of the GSC.

For the d voltage control signal the term $v_{d_g} - \omega_s L i_{q_gsc}$ is added, where $\omega_s = 2\pi \cdot 50$

For the q voltage control signal the term $v_{q_g} + \omega_s L i_{d_gsc}$ is added

Using these additions, the equation of the voltages of the inverter presented in equation (46) are changed to:

$$v'_{d_gsc} + (v_{d_g} - \omega_s L i_{q_gsc}) = r i_{d_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{d_gsc} - \omega_s L i_{q_gsc} - v_{d_g}$$

$$v'_{q_gsc} + (v_{q_g} + \omega_s L i_{d_gsc}) = r i_{q_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{q_gsc} + \omega_s L i_{d_gsc} - v_{q_g}$$

=

$$v_{d_gsc} = r i_{d_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{d_gsc}$$

$$v_{q_gsc} = r i_{q_gsc} + L \frac{d}{dt} i_{q_gsc}$$

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Figure 47 shows the digital implementation of the cross-coupling term elimination.

Figure 47: Digital Implementation of the Cross Coupling Term Elimination

The full control of $(v_{dc})^2$ and Q_{gsc} in the Grid side converter using $dq0$ is deployed as shown in Figure 48.

Figure 48. Full controller of the Grid side converter.

7.2 Simulation Results

Important parameters used in simulations are reported in Table 14 and Table 15. The complete control system is shown in Figure 50. Simulations are done in MATLAB Simulink where all system elements are represented by the model explained before. Three-phase permanent magnet synchronous machine with the parameters reported in Table 14 represents the PMSG of the wind power generation system. Two main structures of inner rotor and outer rotor has been studied thoroughly and finally the inner rotor has been selected. The generator design procedure is explained in detail in [12] as well.

The input to this block is the mechanical torque produced by the wind turbine. Here two generators are being considered that experiencing nominal torque load. Furthermore, a sinusoidal load torque with 50% of nominal torque is added to this load. Considering the generators topology in XROTOR tower, the sinusoidal terms in these two generators are out of phase. The torques acting on generators 1 and 2 are depicted in Figure 49.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
rated power	2.5 MVA	Pole pairs	4
rated speed	375 rpm	rated stator frequency	25 Hz
rated voltage	3300 V	L_d	13.9 mH
flux Linkage	13 Wb	L_q	13.4 mH
inertia	303.69 Kg.m ²	stator phase resistance	0.049 ohm
-	-	damping coefficient	16.21 N.m

Table 14: PMSG parameters

To consider the two generators simultaneously, the mechanical power produced by two turbines are assumed to be sinusoidal curves around the nominal power with the phase difference as shown in Figure 49. This is due to the inherent characteristics of the XROTOR turbine. In all cases, the generators are commanded to keep a constant speed reference so whatever mechanical torque input is reflected as an electrical torque output (Note: the generator speed can be changed based in a full envelop controller for the X-ROTOR, however this step is omitted in this report with the assumption that the full envelope controller is doing an ideal job providing an efficient mechanical torque input to the turbine).

Figure 49. input mechanical torque to the generators.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Line to Line RMS grid voltage	3300	DAB PWM switching frequency	2000 Hz
Grid Frequency	50	Coupling inductor Inductance	265 uH
Nominal dc link voltage of DAB converter	5400	Coupling inductor Resistance	0.001 ohm
Resistance between GSC and AC grid	0.0065 ohm	RT leakage inductance	70 uH
Inductance between GSC and AC grid	0.00208 H	RT Magnetization inductance	3.13 mH

Table 15: simulation parameters

Figure 50. power system and the control system block diagram for a single generator

Figure 51. power system and the control system block diagram for two generators

Since one XROTOR wind turbine consists of two generators, two scenarios have been considered. The first one is independent operation of the generators and their power train. Figure 52 shows the simulation results for this scenario and assuming the constant mechanical input to the generator (2.5 MW). The results include the controlled variables and their reference, as well as the mechanical input and electrical output power of the system. It is evident from the figures that the controlled variable follow the references. In this condition, each DAB converter transfers the rated power of the generator. In order to accommodate fluctuating mechanical power inputs, a DAB converter should be designed for a higher power rating, i.e. 50% higher than 2.5 MW.

Figure 52. simulation results of independent generator operation, 2.5 MW input power

The second scenario is the parallel configuration where two DAB converters share the input power. Here, the fluctuating input mechanical powers of Figure 49 have been considered that means the input power to the generators varies 50% lower and higher the nominal power. Figure 53 shows the system topology for the second scenario where the machine-side dc-links are in parallel.

As could be seen in Figure 54 and Figure 55, the dc link voltages and the reactive power have been controlled as required. Moreover, one generator transfers a constant power while the other one transfers the remaining power. The advantage of this configuration is as shown in Figure 56, the average value of the accumulative mechanical load is 2pu for two generators but, there is no need to over rating of the DAB converters.

Figure 53. simulated power train in MATLAB-Simulink

Figure 54. simulation results of parallel generators operation, oscillating input power, gen #1

Figure 55. simulation results of parallel generators operation, oscillating input power, gen #2

Figure 56. simulation results of parallel generators operation for electrical and mechanical powers (left) and zoomed in (right).

These simulations first show the performance of the power train from PMSGs to network that is 95% efficient while the mechanical slip rings are replaced with wireless power transfers to reduce maintenance costs. In addition, two fluctuating input torques are considered that represent the actual mechanical power of the wind turbine supplied to the generators. To address that, two DABs with parallel connections shared the load properly. In this way, 50% higher mechanical torque could be handled without overrating the converters, as shown by simulation results.

Conclusions

This report presented the full controller design and analysis of the XROTOR drivetrain which included the Generator converters, RT system and grid side converter. The results presented in this report include an improvement of the RT design and a complete analysis using FEA simulation for all relevant losses (electrical, magnetic, thermal). The engineering considerations to develop the RT system were also revised and compared against current magnetic design practices.

With regards to the power electronic topologies, the controllers for such topologies were presented and analysed for each case. In particular the power electronic topology capable to drive power bidirectionally through the RT windings (the DAB converter) was analysed numerically, electrically, and thermally to quantify performance and efficiency. Also, a multi-level three-phase topology called NPC for this power converter has been developed to enable higher voltage and power ratings with lower THD. The simulation results indicate that bidirectional power control can be obtained at the desired switching frequency (2KHz).

The control structure of the different energy conversion stages of the drivetrain was presented along with tuning rules and control design methodologies. The number of different controllers in the drivetrain system included 4 PMSG current controller, 2 PMSG speed controllers, 1 DAB DC voltage controller 1 GSC DC voltage controller 1 Reactive Power Controller and 2 GSC current controller for a total of 11 different controllers.

The results presented in this report indicate that the combined efficiency of the RT and the DAB to enable and control the wireless power transfer in the XROTOR system is 96% which is within the efficiency requirements of the XROTOR project. Furthermore, the designed controller structure, consisting of 11 different controllers, was capable to work in a stable manner to enable energy conversion and transmission through the drivetrain of the XROTOR system. In all cases a cascading control structure consisting of individual PI and IMC controllers controlling different dynamics of the drivetrain was possible since the dynamics of high order plants could be separated in different first-order sections, the time constants between dynamics allowed such separation without interference in the performance of the system.

Appendix A

The parameters used for simulation of 3-phase multi-level DAB converters are listed here:

```

1Fsw= 2e3;    % PWM switching frequency (Hz)
DT= 250e-9;   % Dead time (s)
Scope_Decimation=1; % Scope Decimation
Ts=1e-6;      % Control system sample time (s)
%
Pnom= 3000e3;  % Nominal power (W)
Vnom_HV= 5400; % DC source 1 nominal voltage (V)
Vnom_LV= 5400; % DC source 2 nominal voltage (V)
R_DCsrc1=1e-3; % DC source 1 internal resistance (Ohm)
R_DCsrc2=40e-3; % DC source 2 internal resistance (Ohm)m
%
% Switches
Ron= 3.7500e-04; % FET on-state resistance (Ohm)
Rs= 1e6; % Snubber resistance Rs (Ohm) :
Cs= inf; % Snubber capacitance Cs (F) :
Ron_Diode= 0.035e-3; % Body diode resistance (Ohm)
Vf_Diode= 1.7; % Body diode forward voltage drop (V)
%
% Coupling inductor
L_Inductor= 240e-6; % Inductance (H)
R_Inductor= 1e-3; % Resistance (Ohm)
%
%C_Cap1=140e-6;
%R_Cap2=1e-6;
%C_Cap2=.5e-6;

% Transformer:
N_Tr= 1; % Primary to secondary voltage ratio
Rprim_Tr=0.0133; % Primary resistance (Ohm)
Lprim_Tr= 70e-6; % Primary leakage inductance (H)
Rsec_Tr= 0.0143; % Secondary resistance (Ohm)
Lsec_Tr= 70e-6; % Secondary leakage inductance (H)
Rm_Tr= 10e3; % Magnetization resistance (Ohm)
Lm_Tr= 3.13e-3; % Magnetization inductance (H)
%
% Filters
% High Voltage Capacitor:
C_HV= 20e-6; % Capacitance (F)
RC_HV= 10e-3; % Capacitor ESR (Ohm)
% Low Voltage Capacitor:
C_LV= 20e-6; % Capacitance (F)
RC_LV= 10e-3; % Capacitor ESR (Ohm)

%Thermal modeling parameters
Ts_Power=5e-8;
Ts_Control=5e-8;
IGBT_Rth_jc=0.028;% Changed for Semikron
IGBT_Cth_j=2.6804;
DIODE_Rth_jc=0.049;% Changed for Semikron
DIODE_Cth_j=1.3235;
Tj0=123;
Ad_IGBT=0.99996;
Bd_IGBT=[7.3151,0.37307];
Cd_IGBT=[4.9999e-06;9.8037e-05];
Dd_IGBT=[1.8288e-05,9.3268e-07;-19.607,1.8288e-05];
x0d=2.46e+07;
Ad_Diode=0.99996;

```

```
Bd_Diode=[7.4074,0.75556];
Cd_Diode=[4.9999e-06;4.9019e-05];
Dd_Diode=[1.8519e-05,1.8889e-06;-9.8037,1.8519e-05];
PulseDuration=5e-06;
DIODE_Tj_OnState=[25,125];
DIODE>If_OnState=[0 0.01 14 43 66.5 101 162 250 401 500];
DIODE>Vf_OnState=[0 0.75 1.13 1.4 1.53 1.65 1.81 2 2.25 2.39;0 0.5 0.9 1.2 1.37 1.55 1.81 2.11 2.5 2.71];
Vcc_Esw_Erec=[0,1800];
DIODE>If_Erec=[0 0.01 14 43 66.5 101 162 250 401 450 500];
DIODE>Tj_Erec=[25 125];
%Esw_On=[0 64.9129411764706 124.235294117647 246.917647058824 330 405.317647058824 499.270588235294
601.764705882353 713.576470588235 830.823529411765;0 83.6 160 318 425 522 643 775 919 1070];
%Esw_Off=[0 86.5333333333333 159.866666666667 279.4 330 398.2 456.133333333333 512.6 573.466666666667
631.4;0 118 218 381 450 543 622 699 782 861];
IGBT_Tj_Eoff=[25,125];
IGBT>Ic_Eoff=[0 37.8 99 199 250 300 349 400 451 499];
Vcc_Esw_Off=[0,1800];
Esw_Off=[0 86.5333333333333 159.866666666667 279.4 330 398.2 456.133333333333 512.6 573.466666666667 631.4;0
118 218 381 450 543 622 699 782 861];
Esw_On=[0 64.9129411764706 124.235294117647 246.917647058824 330 405.317647058824 499.270588235294
601.764705882353 713.576470588235 830.823529411765;0 83.6 160 318 425 522 643 775 919 1070];
IGBT_Tj_OnState=[25,125];
IGBT>Ic_Eon=[0 37.8 99 199 250 300 349 400 451 499];
IGBT>Ic_OnState=[0 1 16 77 131 174 276 375 500];
IGBT>Vce_OnState=[0 0.51 1 1.5 1.81 2.04 2.49 2.88 3.37;0 0.5 1 1.71 2.18 2.5 3.11 3.77 4.52]./3;
IGBT_Tj_OnState=[25 125];
Vcc_Esw_On=[0,1800];
IGBT_Tj_Eon=[25,125];
Ts_Simscape=5e-08;
Esw_Erec=[0 50.6196428571429 66.5892857142857 97.2321428571429 124.339285714286 146.142857142857 165
180.321428571429 191.517857142857 198 200.357142857143;0 85.9 113 165 211 248 280 306 325 336 340];
```

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